

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System

Mooring dataset from the South Sandwich Trench

Deliverable D5.1

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Cover sheet: Temperature (°C) time series from the central South Sandwich Trench mooring measured at five different depths.

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History of Changes

Version	Date	Comment	Authors
Version 1	22 September 2025	Submitted version	Rachael Sanders
Version 2	9 March 2026	Editing of the abstract, no ADCPs were deployed, only Nortek Aquadopp Doppler current meters (not profilers). Integration of section 2.1.2 with additional details.	Povl Abrahamsen

1. Publishable summary

In this deliverable, we present a year-long time series of calibrated data from two moorings deployed in the South Sandwich Trench between February 2024 and February 2025. The central mooring included nine instruments at different depths, between approximately 1450 m and 5950 m, providing a time series of temperature, salinity, and current velocities. The mooring was situated at 60°12.85' S, 25°07.36' W in a region of northward export of Weddell Sea Deep Water (WSDW), which goes on to form Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW). Also presented is a time series of temperature and current speed from a second mooring on the western side of the trench, at a location of 60°06.49' S, 25°18.54' W. While this mooring was not fully recovered, a temperature sensor and Doppler current meter were recovered that had been on the seafloor for the entire deployment, at a depth of approximately 3960 m. Each time series has been calibrated, either using the data from casts of nearby conductivity-temperature-depth profilers (CTDs) or by calibrating against the nearest calibrated instrument on the mooring, and quality control has been completed to remove any unreliable data points.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

2.1.1 Description of Dataset

In total, data from nine instruments from the central South Sandwich Trench mooring are presented in the dataset: four time series from Aquadopps consisting of zonal, meridional and vertical velocity, total current speed and direction, and temperature. Two datasets measured using SBE37 Microcats consist of temperature, salinity and pressure, and three datasets measured using an RBRsolo³T consist of only temperature. The complete list of data available from this mooring is shown in Table 1.

Filename	Variable	Depth (m)	Frequency (minutes)	Instrument	Comments
SouthSandwichCentral_CurrentMeter_1454m.nc	Zonal velocity (ms ⁻¹) Meridional velocity (ms ⁻¹) Vertical velocity (ms ⁻¹) Current speed (ms ⁻¹) Temperature (°C) Current direction (°)	1454	10	Aquadopp DW	
SouthSandwichCentral_Temperature_Salinity_1455m.nc	Temperature (°C) Salinity (psu)	1455	10	SBE37-SM Microcat	Salinity data removed between 14th March and 8th

Filename	Variable	Depth (m)	Frequency (minutes)	Instrument	Comments
	Pressure (dbar)				April 2024
SouthSandwichCentral_Temperature_2119m.nc	Temperature (°C)	2119	1	RBRsolo ³ T	
SouthSandwichCentral_CurrentMeter_2952m.nc	Zonal velocity (ms ⁻¹) Meridional velocity (ms ⁻¹) Vertical velocity (ms ⁻¹) Current speed (ms ⁻¹) Temperature (°C) Current direction (°)	2952	10	Aquadopp DW	
SouthSandwichCentral_Temperature_2119m.nc	Temperature (°C)	3700	1	RBRsolo ³ T	
SouthSandwichCentral_CurrentMeter_4452m.nc	Zonal velocity (ms ⁻¹) Meridional velocity (ms ⁻¹) Vertical velocity (ms ⁻¹) Current speed (ms ⁻¹) Temperature (°C) Current direction (°)	4452	10	Aquadopp DW	
SouthSandwichCentral_Temperature_5200m.nc	Temperature (°C)	5200	1	RBRsolo ³ T	
	Zonal velocity (ms ⁻¹) Meridional velocity (ms ⁻¹)	5944	10	Aquadopp DW	

Filename	Variable	Depth (m)	Frequency (minutes)	Instrument	Comments
SouthSandwichCentral_CurrentMeter_5944m.nc	Vertical velocity (ms^{-1}) Current speed (ms^{-1}) Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) Current direction ($^{\circ}$)				
SouthSandwichCentral_Temperature_Salinity_5945m.nc	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) Salinity (psu) Pressure (dbar)	5945	10	SBE37-SM Microcat	No salinity data available after 4th July 2024

Table 1: List of data files available from the central South Sandwich Trench mooring and an overview of the variables they contain.

Only two datasets are available from the western South Sandwich Trench mooring, and are listed in Table 2: a time series of temperature from an SBE39, and current velocity data from an Aquadopp. Both instruments were lying on the seafloor for the entire deployment, and the individual velocity components from the Aquadopp are therefore unusable.

Filename	Variable	Depth (m)	Frequency (minutes)	Instrument	Comments
SouthSandwichWest_CurrentMeter_3957m.nc	Speed (ms^{-1}) Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	3957	10	Aquadopp DW	Instrument was on or near the seafloor - individual velocity components not reliable
SouthSandwichWest_Temperature_3957m.nc	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	3957	10	SBE39	Instrument was on or near the seafloor

Table 2: List of data files available from the western South Sandwich Trench mooring and an overview of the variables they contain.

2.1.2 Instrument Calibration and Quality Control

Once downloaded, calibration and quality control was completed when necessary. After recovery of the moorings, each Microcat was attached to the ship's CTD frame for a deep cast, for the data to be calibrated against the CTD data. The offsets required to correct temperature, conductivity and pressure were calculated as those that most reduced the difference between the values recorded by the instrument and those recorded by the CTD itself. Salinity was then recalculated using the corrected conductivity and temperature. Since temperature sensors tend to be much more stable, the temperature time series measured using

RBRSoloTs or SBE39s were only calibrated if offsets had previously been calculated. The calibrated time series of temperature is shown in Figure 1.

When an Aquadopp was within 30 m of a Microcat, the temperature and pressure measured by the Aquadopp were calibrated against the already calibrated data from the Microcat. The magnetic declination at the mooring position was also calculated (-7.4°), and the zonal and meridional velocities and current direction were corrected accordingly. The current speed measured by each instrument is shown in Figure 2.

Once calibrated, the data was checked, and any untrustworthy data was removed; an issue with the conductivity sensor on the deepest SBE37 Microcat of the central mooring means that any salinity data after July 2024 is unusable and so has been removed from the dataset. A bad section of data was also removed from the salinity measured by the shallower Microcat between 14th March and 8th April 2024, when there was a sudden drop in salinity. Due to some large spikes in the salinity data, any points that were more than ± 10 times the standard deviation from the mean were also automatically removed. The final salinity time series is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 1: Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$) time series from the central South Sandwich Trench mooring measured at five different depths.

Fig. 2: Time series of current speed (ms⁻¹) at the central South Sandwich Trench mooring measured by the four Aquadopps positioned at different depths.

Fig. 3: Time series of salinity (psu) measured by the two SBE37 Microcats on the central South Sandwich Trench mooring. The data points in blue have been removed after quality control checks.

The instruments from the western mooring were most likely on the seafloor for the entire one-year deployment, and the tilt of the Aquadopp current meter was more than 30° from the vertical. When tilted

beyond this point, the instrument cannot measure its orientation, so while the Doppler current sensor can measure currents in the instrument reference frame, these cannot be transformed into earth coordinates. Since each beam amplitude measured by the instrument looked OK, the absolute speed was calculated and compared with that measured by the deepest Aquadopp on the central mooring. The measured current speeds are very similar, giving us confidence that the speed measured at the western site is reliable, though the direction of the current cannot be ascertained. The temperature sensor recovered from the mooring was not biofouled, and so the temperature data are also considered reliable. Both are shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Data from the two recovered instruments from the western South Sandwich Trench mooring: current speed measured by an Aquadopp and temperature measured by an SBE39. Both instruments were at the seafloor (3957 m) for the entire deployment.

2.1.3 Deviations from the original plan

Unfortunately, a second mooring in the west of the trench was not fully recovered (see Sanders and Abrahamsen, 2025). While two instruments were recovered, it appears they were lying on the seafloor for the entire deployment period, and so not all the data are usable. However, the data that are considered reliable are still included in this dataset. There was also a large offset and drift in the salinity measured by the deepest Microcat on the central mooring, meaning that the salinity data from July 2024 onwards are not usable, so there is only one shallower time series of salinity available.

2.2 References

Sanders, R. and Abrahamsen, P., 2025. Recovery of moorings in South Sandwich Trench (Milestone MS10). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15190925>

2.3 Open Science

The data underlying this deliverable are deposited on Zenodo, with tags pointing to OCEAN ICE. The data are embargoed until 30th September 2026, due to a publication currently being written using the data. The DOI

is the following: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17141551>. Data will be made available in open access as soon as the publication is accepted.

3. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objectives of the project as described in the description of the action.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica, particularly relating to ice sheet-ocean interaction and deep water formation and export.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by providing new information about the WSDW that is exported through the South Sandwich Trench, which then goes on to form a significant part of the AABW found in the deepest layer of the global oceans. While there has been long-term monitoring of the WSDW exported through Orkney Passage over recent decades, this is the first deep time series of data in the South Sandwich Trench, providing information about variability in the water mass.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

Data consolidation and delivery will be achieved through close integration with SOOS, EMODnet and Copernicus data delivery services and will follow FAIR principles and be INSPIRE compliant. Direct partnership with SOOS, SAMOC, EPB, EU Polar Cluster, EU-Polarnet 2, and other European and international programmes, as well as the high-level involvement of investigators in international science coordination, climate assessment and policy bodies, will maximise the reach and impact of OCEAN ICE.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective as the mooring datasets will be published with open access on Zenodo.